

Designüberlegungen für BBMRI-ERIC CS-ITs dezentrale Architektur

Designing BBMRI-ERIC CS-IT's decentralized architecture

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Abstract. The more biobanks with relatively good quality data that participate in the BBMRI-ERIC research infrastructure, the more resources are available for research throughout Europe, which facilitate the access to biological resources and support biomolecular and medical research. This study aims to demonstrate how such a research network can benefit from an integrated, harmonized, distributed and decentralized search architecture. The information system proposed is composed by integrated central and local components, which include a centralized Metadata Repository (MDR) where the clinical metadata items are defined, a Sample Locator that enables sample-level data discovery and Connectors, which enable the interaction, at the biobank local level, with the biobank systems. The combination of these components with an European single sign-on system potentiates the participation of different biobanks and the communication and sample sharing between researchers and biobankers through a federated search architecture, while respecting data ownership and data privacy. Biobankers can share pseudonymised data on a request basis. The federated search is, however, a complex concept that becomes challenging to introduce, so it should be kept as simple as possible, designed towards data privacy and data ownership, respecting the requirements from all participant biobanks and countries. Further challenges include the assistance to biobanks on the integration process, which are mitigated by the delivery of semantic mapping tools that biobanks could use, even with limited IT knowledge.

Keywords. Biobanking, BBMRI-ERIC CS-IT, Federated Search, Decentralized Search, Samples, Data Protection, Metadata Repository, Data Ownership, Secondary Use, Phenotyping

Introduction

Biobanks provide information that help understanding human diseases. Biological samples and related data is essential for the development of diagnostics, drugs and for the development of health research. Consequently, the close collaboration between researchers, biobankers, patient representative communities, biotech and pharma industry is essential for a better prevention, diagnostics, therapy and for the overall understanding of diseases. Enabling researchers to reach biobank resources at the

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European level will facilitate the access to biological resources and support high-quality biomolecular and medical research.

Nevertheless, identifying bio samples for patients that match certain criteria is a challenge. Not only are samples or patients for e.g. rare diseases very difficult to find; it is also challenging to harmonize the medical data describing the respective sample donors and query it across multiple biobanks and borders due to the high heterogeneity.

BBMRI-ERIC [1], a pan-European Biobanking and BioMolecular resources Research Infrastructure, is a distributed biomedical and life science infrastructure for sustainable storage and dissemination of biobank samples and associated data in Europe, which aims to address the above challenges. It will provide access to the collections of partner biobanks and biomolecular resources, their expertise and services on a non-economic basis. The BBMRI-ERIC “Common Service IT” (CS-IT) has the mission to deliver expertise, services and tools relevant to the pursuance of tasks and activities of BBMRI-ERIC. It is complemented by the H2020 INFRADEV-3 project ADOPT, designed to accelerate development and deployment of tools needed for BBMRI-ERIC.

In the scope of BBMRI-ERIC CS-IT, a federated search will enable querying simultaneously multiple biobanks that are running different biobanking software solutions based on heterogeneous data structures [2]. The federated architecture [3] supports specifying search queries based on items defined in the Metadata Repository and the asynchronous interaction with the participating biobanks. A description of the research and the contact information of the inquiring partners complements the request, which is made available to all participating biobanks. Locally and under the biobankers’ control, the connector is able to retrieve the query and it is also able to receive, still locally (no data is being shared), pseudonymised [4] sample data. These results are presented to the person in charge of the biobank, together with the research description and the inquirer’s contact information. Finally, the data owner decides what to reply. The response process can be automated for trusted requesters, if the local data/biobank owner desires. However, no data is shared without the explicit consent of the data owner. The connector will offer a built-in component to pseudonymise data and also match data (regarding the same patient/proband) locally from different databases.

The development of the BBMRI-ERIC platform is still at an early stage, however, the infrastructure benefits from previous research (e.g. Molgenis, OSSE [5], MDR, EHR4CR [6], i2b2/IDRT [8, 9]). By also reusing existing components wherever possible, we aim to fully tackle challenges beyond implementation, such as data protection, data integration, legal and semantic aspects.

Material and Methods

BBMRI-ERIC CS-IT is organized in eight work packages (“WP”) and the federated search involves mainly the Sample Locator (WP2), Connector (WP5) and Semantic Harmonization Tools (WP8). The Sample Locator aims at providing availability information of samples and sample-related data from the biobanks to the researchers (consumers) through a federated querying mechanism. This component will be integrated with mechanisms developed in WP8, in order to deal with the highly heterogeneous data structures of European biobanks and clinical data repositories. Such tools will include approaches to map data elements (content) and database schemas (syntax). This approach extends the BBMRI-ERIC Directory (WP1), which is a central catalogue-like solution that only provides summary level, aggregated data. In contrast, the sample locator enables the processing of requests on a sample-based level, therefore

allowing complex sample identification algorithms. To provide the biobanks full control over individual data requests, the architecture design consists of a distributed federated system, which allows participating biobanks to accept or reject queries, or even “pull the plug” at any time.

The “Medizinische Informatik in der Translationalen Onkologie (G230)” work group at the German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ) has already been developing federated search architectures in the scope of other projects, such as the Open Source Registry Software Solution (OSSE) [5] and the “Deutsches Konsortium für Translationale Krebsforschung” (DKTK) Clinical Communication Platform IT (CCP-IT). This same work group is represented in BBMRI-ERIC CS-IT in WP2 - Sample Locator. Likewise, the Institute for Medical Informatics of the University Erlangen-Nuremberg, who has been working on several projects on clinical research and data harmonization, such as EHR4CR [6, 7] and and i2b2 (respectively the German extension as an Integrated Data Repository Toolkit: IDRT) [8, 9], is partner in WP8 - Harmonization Tools. Materials and methods used in BBMRI-ERIC will therefore benefit from the work done on software components that were developed by these teams and delivered open-source. These components will, however, have to be extended or changed to adapt to the european-level context and BBMRI-ERIC specific requirements.

Metadata Repository (MDR)

The Metadata Repository application holds data that is commonly known by the term metadata, which can simply be understood as “data about data”. It includes the definition, detailed description, validations and types of data used to define samples and correlated information in the scope of BBMRI-ERIC. As an example, “Surgery date” is a data element which could be described as “the day of the month and year of a surgical procedure”, has the type technically named as “Date” and can be validated by the format “dd.mm.yyyy”.

The MDR follows the standard ISO/IEC 11179, Information Technology -- Metadata registries (MDR), especially the “Registry metamodel and basic attributes”, which describes what kind of metadata is needed and the structure of metadata registries. It allows storing metadata and enables consumers to retrieve it. All kinds of data can be defined formally by annotating appropriate metadata and these formal definitions are made broadly available in a central MDR. Besides a graphical user interface (GUI), the MDR features a REST interface that can be used by other applications.

As all metadata is defined in the MDR and multiple components access it, implementing cache on the MDR consumers will be crucial. Cache on the Directory, Negotiator, Connector and Sample Locator will highly increase the performance in these components and also in the MDR. It will also enable other systems to continue running flawlessly even if there is a temporary failure in the MDR. The interfaces between the different components are implemented using the Representational State Transfer (REST) paradigm.

To make it even simpler to integrate with the MDR, a Java library has been created to query for data elements naming, definition and validation information. The *Samplly.MDRClient* library, as it is called, can be reused in Java projects to get sets of data that describe and give information about other data (i.e. metadata), from the MDR, through REST calls. Applications based on Java Server Faces (JSF) can also use *Samplly.MDRFaces* - a JSF library which eases the user interface design of web

applications where the respective data model relies on well-defined data elements. Especially in case of systems for electronic data capturing, where the necessary data model is not known beforehand and can even vary over time, the user interface has to be easily adjustable. This often means the user instead of the developer designs the various forms for data entry and therefore an easy to use mechanism has to be provided. By using *Samplify.MDRFaces* the developer can focus on the implementation of that mechanism, e.g. some editor component, but does not have to cope with the visualization of every single data element as for that is taken care of automatically.

Sample Locator

The Sample Locator (WP2) aims at finding samples and sample-related data (possibly including, for instance, clinical & imaging data, phenotypic data in the broad sense, etc.) from the biobanks through a federated search mechanism. The Sample Locator will be integrated with information model and terminology mapping tools, developed by WP8, in order to support the heterogeneity of the biobank data structures across Europe. This approach complements the BBMRI-ERIC Directory (WP1), which is a catalogue-like solution with summary-level data and flat data model (preventing answering full questions, i.e. those including full Boolean logic, at the sample/individual level), by enabling the processing of requests on a sample-based level and giving the biobanks full control over individual data requests.

The federated search concept supports specifying search queries based on items from the metadata repository (WP8) and the asynchronous interaction with the participating biobanks. Along with the query, the request shall include a description of the research (or clarifying why the user is searching for specific samples) and the contact information of the inquiring partners, which is made available to all participating biobanks.

The request interface of the local biobanks, the connector, retrieves the query and the results, locally. Sample-level results, together with the research description and the inquirer's contact information, are presented to the data owner, who decides what to reply to each request.

Connector

The Connector is the BBMRI-ERIC CS-IT software component that runs on the biobank network and is under the control of the network administrator. It includes a software interface that is able to retrieve pending research inquiries from the Sample Locator, queries local data sources (either through its API that can be used by local BIMS (Biobank Information Management System) or on pseudonymised data persisted on an accessible database with a BBMRI-ERIC predefined data structure) and enables data owners to manage research requests.

An included user interface (UI) allows the data owner to visualize the research description and the inquirer's contact information. Moreover, the Connector can automatically display the results of the search request so that the data owner can see exactly what data is being requested. The response process can be automated for trusted requesters (e.g. share all request results data with Researcher A), if the local data/biobank owner so desires. However, no data is shared without the explicit consent of the data owner. The UI also allows to initiate the negotiation (see Negotiator) with the researcher.

All data managed by the connector is already pseudonymised - no identifiable data is managed or shared. The Connector has a REST interface with the local biobanks that

supplies queries (based on metadata) and gets the results (sample data). The REST interface description will be made publicly available to ease the integration with biobank management systems. There are plans to develop tools to help biobanks map BBMRI-ERIC metadata to local data structures.

Negotiator

The Negotiator is a component that moderates the data requesting and access process. It is a communication platform between researchers and biobankers regarding sample requests.

Considering the sample search from the Sample Locator, a request triggers a data sharing negotiation process between the researcher and the participating biobanks. The Negotiator enables the refinement, based on discussion, of the search requests for each specific biobank. Biobank sample-level data is shared only through the Negotiator. In the case the data owner has previously given access on some specific sample level data to the researcher (trust relationship), the data would be shared automatically through the Negotiator.

At an initial development phase of the Negotiator, it will work as an Internet forum, or message board - an online discussion site where researchers and biobankers can hold conversations in the form of posted messages. This way the researchers who search for aggregated data in the Directory can easily discover, for instance, which participating biobanks have the samples or data needed for a particular research.

Results

At the time of writing this abstract, the official version of the BBMRI-ERIC CS-IT architecture conceptualization is close to be concluded. It describes the philosophy, decisions, constraints, justifications, significant elements, and any other overarching aspects of the system that shape the design and implementation. Hence, it includes the main results we have obtained up to this stage.

The architecture considerations described in this abstract are mainly related to BBMRI-ERIC CS-IT federated search: the Sample Locator, Negotiator, Connector and Harmonization Services, including the Metadata Repository. These abstractions are depicted in the diagram below.

Figure 1. Conceptualization of the BBMRI-ERIC CS-IT architecture

All the components depicted on top (Directory, Sample Locator, Negotiator and Connector) get data from the harmonization services, which is expressed by having the harmonization services as a horizontal layer, supporting the components above it. Due to the intensive communication with the metadata repository (MDR) all the components that integrate with it shall support cache.

The direction of the arrows represents the high-level interaction between the components, it is not a detailed message diagram or a technical representation. For instance, although an inquiry is defined at the Sample Locator and will get to the Connector, the Connector shall actually be polling the Sample Locator for inquiries. This is done for security reasons and to overcome biobank networks restrictions on communication, to ease biobank integration with BBMRI.

The Connector, although developed and distributed by BBMRI-ERIC CS-IT, is made to run on the biobank networks (local environment) and it is offered to be operated under the control of the biobanks. This will ensure that no data is shared without the permission of the data owner. There will be an extraction, transformation, and loading (ETL) process that will take place when the data is transferred from the biobank systems's database to the Connector's Data Warehouse, and it involves data pseudonymisation - [Figure 2. Integration of a Biobank with the Connector, Sample...](#)

Figure 2. Integration of a Biobank with the Connector, Sample Locator and Metadata Repository (MDR)

A central user/group authentication and authorisation will be implemented so that permissions can be managed centrally and users can login to all applications using a single sign-on (SSO). As a result, the navigation through the different independent systems is transparent for the users and the system integration is secure.

The Harmonization Services play an important role between the central components and the local components, namely on the requests created on the Sample Locator and the sharing of data and communication through the Negotiator. The data harmonization tools enable, through the Metadata Repository and Terminology Mapping Tool, the communication between the different systems and heterogenous

biobank data structures. The BBMRI-ERIC metadata definition will need to be mapped to the local data structures, so that the integration between the connector and the local BIMS can be automated.

Discussion

There are multiple database management systems and tools that biobanks use and it is also common that biobanks create proprietary software for their activities. Despite the development of standards such as ICD-10 or SNOMED, biobanks run on different data structures and systems. Even when dealing with the same kind of data, biobanks persist their clinical data on different structures, naming and units. For successful research across data in multiple biobanks an efficient syntactic and semantic harmonization platform is needed for the biobanks to be able to communicate on the same semantic platform.

Biobanks are often intransigent, incapable or not allowed to give away their data to be managed by another entity that persists clinical data, centrally (not in the biobank private network), from different biobanks under the same platform and data structure. In these cases the biobanks demand ownership on the data and control over privacy, although they are usually willing to share pseudonymised data on specific samples and for individual research projects. A federated architecture is, therefore, recommended as it allows interoperability, harmonization and information sharing between biobankers and researchers while maintaining the biobank autonomy.

Despite the advantages of the federated search compared to a centralized approach, it is still challenging to figure out the systems' inner workings and to introduce its technical architecture. The need to cover information privacy requirements, data ownership, semantic harmonization and interoperability between multiple biobanks naturally contributes to a more complex solution that would be possible to achieve without the above mentioned constraints. The proposed architecture is therefore designed to be as simple as possible and to reuse already available, solid open source software components, gradually improving the complete system. Data privacy is also a major priority for the design of the integrated system.

So that BBMRI-ERIC can reach a greater number of biobanks, the integration process should be supported. Although the CS-IT architecture covers already most important aspects of interoperability and harmonization, the biobanks need to work on data transformations of sample data. That is to say that BBMRI-ERIC metadata items defined in the MDR have to be mapped to the local data items in the biobanks' databases, so that locally, at the biobank level, is it possible to automatically interpret incoming queries. The creation of mappings is very time-consuming [10, 11] and should be supported by software tools where possible. Mapping tools could help biobanks to map their local terms to the MDR metadata items. It should be done, as far as possible, in a way that biobanks would be able to participate in the BBMRI-ERIC CS-IT federated search even with limited IT knowledge.

In a future release a Sample Locator Genomic Query service will be developed to allow biobanks to harness the molecular information they have available to help researchers in sample selection. The service will be based on genomic information associated with the managed biosamples and support simple query semantics (i.e., at the level of allele presence at a given genomic position).

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